

Response to RFI GEC-2680-12152021

Alaska Satellite Facility
Wade Albright, ASF Director and DAAC Manager
Dr. Franz Meyer, ASF Chief Scientist

Background

The Alaska Satellite Facility (ASF) has been the US science community's primary source for Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data for over 30 years, and is currently one of twelve NASA Distributed Active Archive Centers (DAAC) responsible for managing a data archive for NASA. ASF is the SAR DAAC, in that ASF hosts SAR data, and employs a staff with SAR expertise. In addition, because SAR data products are extremely large and difficult to use, ASF has developed expertise in large-scale data processing, especially in AWS, in order to facilitate use of SAR by the scientific and other communities.

ASF currently maintains an archive of SAR data of over 15 petabytes, over 13 of which are stored in the cloud, in AWS S3 buckets. ASF was one of the first NASA DAACs to move to the cloud, and has been a leader in the NASA community in moving data into AWS. Over the past several years, ASF has distributed over 50 petabytes of data to users from AWS.

Over the past several years ASF has been heavily involved with the science community developing cloud-based solutions that improve the science utilization of the AWS-based ASF archive. The Hybrid Pluggable Processing Pipeline (HyP3) was developed as a scalable cloud-based system capable of processing large volumes of SAR data quickly and cost-effectively. The system is easily extendable with new science algorithms and has been used in many research projects, including several operational processing campaigns related to the current ITS_LIVE MEaSURES project. As part of this project, science code was embedded into the ASF HyP3 system and used to quickly process over 2 million Landsat-8 pairs in 2 weeks of wall-clock time, for less than \$25,000, approximately 1.2 cents per pair. HyP3 provided the capability to complete these project tasks on schedule and was well under budget.

ASF's OpenSARlab platform is a second science-support service developed by ASF. The platform enables collaborative development of algorithms using a shared environment with Jupyter Notebooks. Moreover, the platform runs in the cloud, so that algorithms leveraging data in the cloud are run next to the data. The system automatically adds additional compute resources as more users log into the system. It has a broad range of applications from collaborative code development to capacity building and user training.

The combination of OpenSARlab, the HyP3 system, and the existing DAAC infrastructure at ASF make ASF uniquely suited to facilitate building algorithms using an open, collaborative process, seamlessly and cost-effectively running at a regional or global scale, archiving the generated data, and providing rich access under free and open data policies.

Data Processing System Architecture

The ASF HyP3 system is a proven system capable of processing high volumes of data quickly and cost-effectively, and supports easy integration of new algorithms. The system is built using AWS Batch, DynamoDB, and Lambda, and numerous other AWS services.

The HyP3 system is readily deployable into new AWS accounts, and the code for the system is stored in a public repository on GitHub. Processing algorithms used by the system are developed as Docker containers, making incorporation of new or updated algorithms as seamless as possible.

The HyP3 system works most effectively when it runs in AWS next to the source data for processing. ASF uses this system for its operational On Demand processing service, where Sentinel-1 SLCs are pulled for processing into Level 2 RTC and InSAR products. Because the system runs in the same AWS region as the Sentinel-1 SLC data archive, no egress costs are incurred until the user downloads the final, much smaller, products from Amazon S3 storage. Because the processing costs are low with HyP3, users leveraging the On Demand service save themselves time, storage space, and the inconvenience of processing the data on their own, and ASF and NASA save the egress costs of downloading the large Sentinel-1 SLC data products.

Open Science

ASF's OpenSARlab platform is ideally suited to support Open Science. The platform enables collaborative development of algorithms in the cloud using a shared environment with Jupyter Notebooks.

OpenSARlab has been used by the NISAR Science Team as part of their Level 3 algorithm development activities. The cloud-based nature and consistent platform allowed the NASA and ISRO science teams to collaborate more effectively.

OpenSARlab has been used for many capacity building and training activities over the last several years, including the recent InSAR training courses conducted in collaboration with UNAVCO, where over a hundred students were able to take the course entirely virtually. It has also been used in several courses at the University of Alaska, including the SAR course that has enrollment from countries all over the world. In each of these cases, students did not need to struggle with the installation difficulties normally associated with SAR processing software, so the course could immediately proceed to discussion of data processing and analysis, rather than spend time debugging user installations on their local hardware.

OpenSARlab is a cloud-based system, where users work with Jupyter Notebooks on systems running in the cloud. The environment can be easily deployed in an end-user's AWS account. Users who wish to do processing on their own systems can also export the OpenSARlab processing environment as a Docker container to deploy locally. Processing done on local or other cloud-based systems will produce identical products as those generated within OpenSARlab.

Component Technologies

The combination of OpenSARlab and the HyP3 system creates a pathway for algorithms to be collaboratively developed and validated with OpenSARlab, and then operationalized and executed on regional or global scales with HyP3. The final output products of processing are stored in S3 buckets and are ready to hand off to a NASA DAAC such as ASF for ingest and archive using the Cumulus ingest system. Cumulus is in use for currently operational ingest systems at ASF as well as several other DAACs. The Cumulus ingest system was built to allow consistent and rapid development of new ingest pipelines, especially for products delivered to the DAAC via S3.

NASA DAACs including ASF have begun work on service offerings through the Harmony framework. Datasets supported by Harmony will allow subsetting, reprojection, and other common temporal and spatial manipulations to be requested by the user with OGC-compliant API calls. Cloud-based datasets will be prioritized for support for use with Harmony by NASA.

Datasets stored in CMR support creation of STAC catalog metadata, and in the future support for Dask and Zarr will be added. These modern data access patterns allow pixel-level access to data products, and represent the future of how data in the cloud will be accessed.

This combination of tools thus allows new data products to be developed and validated collaboratively by subject matter experts, generated in a cost-effective and reproducible manner, and ingested at a DAAC for permanent archival with standard DAAC tools. The entire process results in completely reproducible science products where the code is open and available as Jupyter Notebooks, and the data is generated and archived completely in the cloud. If the source data products are also hosted in the cloud, then the entire product lifecycle from initial development, regional or global processing, through availability to users occurs completely in the cloud.

As part of the process of data archival at a DAAC, the notebooks developed to produce the data with OpenSARlab become part of the standard support offerings a DAAC provides for datasets. This meets one of the key goals of the open science initiative, where any user has complete visibility into the source data products, the algorithms, and the ancillary data that went into the generation of the data products. Because OpenSARlab provides the ability to use the same processing environment on their own systems, a user can readily perform the processing using their own systems and generate identical products to those generated by OpenSARlab and the standard products that are archived at the DAAC.

Downstream Interoperability

ASF is a NASA DAAC and any dataset ingested into the ASF archive receives support in the form of documentation and tutorials hosted on the ASF website, first-level support for user questions about the dataset, reliable data delivery systems, and rich user interfaces that allow users to search the dataset and other related datasets. Metadata is stored in the NASA Common Metadata Repository along with thousands of other datasets, and is searchable using the NASA Earthdata Search, in addition to ASF's more dataset-specific search offerings.

Links

1. ASF: <https://asf.alaska.edu/>
2. ASF HyP3: <https://github.com/ASFHyP3>
3. OpenSARlab: <https://github.com/ASFOpenSARlab>
4. OpenSARlab Jupyter notebooks:
<https://github.com/ASFOpenSARlab/opensarlab-notebooks>
5. ITS_LIVE MEaSURES project: <https://its-live.jpl.nasa.gov/>
6. AutoRIFT software for ITS_LIVE: <https://github.com/nasa-jpl/autoRIFT>
7. UNAVCO InSAR Short Course:
<https://www.unavco.org/news/2021-insar-processing-and-time-series-analysis-short-course/>
8. UAF SAR course using OpenSARlab: <https://radar.community.uaf.edu/>
9. The Cumulus Framework: <https://nasa.github.io/cumulus/docs/cumulus-docs-readme>
10. The Harmony Framework: <https://harmony.earthdata.nasa.gov/>